

Towards Ethical Urban Data Science: a Human-Centric, Interdisciplinary Approach to Shaping future Cities

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Abstract: As urbanization accelerates, cities face increasingly complex challenges that demand innovative and ethical solutions. Urban data science has emerged as a crucial tool to address these challenges through data-driven approaches. This paper advocates for a human-centric, interdisciplinary approach to ethical urban data science, emphasizing its vital role in shaping the future of cities. By integrating insights from sociology, psychology, economics, and urban planning, the paper explores the ethical implications of data collection, analysis, and decision-making processes in urban environments. A comprehensive bibliometric analysis is conducted to examine the existing literature, identifying key trends, influential authors, and seminal works.

The findings underscore the importance of transparency, accountability, and fairness in urban data science practices. The paper also highlights the need for obtaining informed consent, protecting individual privacy, and involving diverse communities in decision-making. Additionally, the potential of emerging technologies, such as blockchain, to enhance data security and transparency is discussed, though the paper cautions that these technologies must be implemented responsibly. The authors conclude by outlining future research directions, emphasizing the ongoing need for ethical considerations as urban data science evolves.

By adopting ethical governance and interdisciplinary collaboration, cities can harness the potential of data-driven research while safeguarding the rights and well-being of their residents, ultimately contributing to the development of smarter, more equitable, and sustainable urban environments.

Keywords: Ethical Urban- Data Science-HCA Human-Centric Approach-Interdisciplinary-Methods-Smart Cities -Ethical Implications-Urban Planning

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Introduction

Urbanization is a rapidly growing global phenomenon, with a majority of the world's population living in urban areas. As cities continue to expand, they face increasingly complex challenges, such as resource and transportation management and enhancing resident well-being. Urban Data Science has emerged as a means of addressing these challenges through informed, data-driven approaches. This literature review explores Ethical Urban Data Science and its pivotal role in developing smarter cities.

Urban Data Science involves collating, combining, and evaluating extensive datasets derived from urban sources such as sensors, gadgets, automobiles, structures, and even human actions. Its primary goal is to address significant urban problems, boost quality of life, enhance city operations, and promote eco-friendly practices. However, two primary challenges face this area of study: efficiently managing the large daily data output and effectively implementing data-driven insights into practical urban solutions and theories.

To improve understanding of complex urban processes, researchers utilize data analytics, computer modeling, and simulation techniques. Urban Data Science is a multidisciplinary field encompassing sociology, psychology, economics, and urban planning.

However, ethical issues arise, including concerns about privacy and potential data analysis biases. The large-scale collection of data on individuals and their urban activities, without adequate informed consent, raises significant privacy concerns. Urban data science algorithms may unintentionally perpetuate social biases, leading to biased outcomes in data analysis and decision-making processes. Thus, it is crucial to implement human-centered methodologies that prioritize individual rights, informed consent, and diverse representation in decision-making. Blockchain technology is currently being explored as a promising solution to enhance data security and transparency in response to these ethical concerns. Ensuring data security and protecting citizens' privacy are critical for building trust and promoting accountability in data-driven urban development. Blockchain technology can assist in these efforts.

Moreover, this review underscores the pivotal role of ethics in promoting transparent, equitable, and accountable data-driven urban development. By considering ethical implications, Urban Data Science can assist in developing more intelligent cities that prioritize the well-being and privacy of their residents while utilizing data to drive positive change. In the following sections, we will explore the field of Urban Data Science, analyze ethical considerations, advocate for a people-centric approach, and scrutinize the intersection of technology and urban planning in relation to the development of intelligent cities.

I- Literature review :

1. Understanding Urban Data :

Urban data science involves the acquisition, integration, and analysis of large and diverse datasets from various sources within urban environments, including sensors, devices, vehicles, buildings, and even humans. Its objective is to address key challenges faced by cities and develop mutually beneficial solutions that enhance the urban landscape, improve quality of life, and optimize city operational systems. Challenges and Opportunities in Urban Data Science Urban data science encounters two primary challenges: managing and interpreting the voluminous data generated regularly and conveying the insights derived from the data into practical outcomes and novel urban theories.

This interdisciplinary field employs analytical thinking, computational modeling, and simulation techniques to investigate, comprehend, and illustrate urban processes (Bibri, 2019). Urban data science aims to address the complex challenges cities face, including transportation, resource consumption, housing affordability, and aging infrastructure. The increasing availability of urban data provides new opportunities for city governments and social scientists to conduct data-driven research, enhance their understanding of cities, improve their efficiency, and enhance the lives of their residents. The advent of big data and smart data has fueled a renaissance in urban science. Big data signifies the continually growing amount, variety, and speed of data produced in urban settings, collected from sources such as social media, sensors, and mobile devices. This multiplicity of information offers insights into numerous aspects of city life. Smart data refers to a subset of big data that has been processed and analyzed to unveil valuable insights and patterns. Technical abbreviations will be explained upon first use.

Common academic sections will be included and regular author and institution formatting shall be maintained. The language will be clear, objective, and value-neutral with a passive tone and impersonal construction. High-level, standard language and consistent technical terms shall be utilized, and common sentence structure maintained. A clear structure with logical progression and causal connections between statements shall be aimed for to avoid bias, subjective evaluations, and emotional and figurative language. Precise word choice will be prioritized utilizing subject-specific vocabulary when it conveys the meaning more precisely than a similar non-technical term. The text will be free from grammatical errors, spelling mistakes, and punctuation errors while adhering to style guides with consistent citation. Contractions, colloquial words, informal expressions, and unnecessary jargon will be avoided, and positions on subjects established through hedging. Big data scientists conduct research that surpasses the mere gathering and analysis of large and intricate

datasets. These scientists also formulate algorithms that sort, reveal patterns, and make sense of the data. (Munawar et al. , 2022) These algorithms are founded on assumptions about the operational structures of cities and play a crucial role in revealing their underlying structures and movements. The interdisciplinary nature of urban data science is indispensable in confronting cities' challenges. The all-encompassing nature of urban data science allows for a more comprehensive comprehension of cities and their intricacies. Furthermore, urban data science acknowledges the ethical implications of working with urban data. (Redden,2018)

2. Ethical Implications in Urban Data Science

The collection and analysis of urban data raise significant ethical concerns. As urban data science continues to develop and reshape smarter cities, addressing these ethical implications becomes crucial to ensure an overall positive impact of data-driven research. It is vital to safeguard personal data and uphold the right to privacy while reaping the benefits of advanced data analysis. Privacy is among the primary ethical concerns in urban data science. (Urban data science relies heavily on collecting large amounts of data about individuals and their activities within the city (Saeed Ali & Kaya, 2019; Hawthorne, 2021).

This information comprises location data from mobile devices or social media posts, among other personal data. Analyzing this data without acquiring informed consent from individuals could pose serious privacy concerns.) Ethical considerations present in urban data science include potential biases and discrimination. Algorithms employed in this field are developed based on assumptions about how cities function, which can be influenced by societal biases and prejudices. This can result in biased outcomes in data analysis and decision-making processes. (Lund & Wang, 2022) Urban data scientists must prioritize addressing ethical concerns and reducing bias and discrimination in their research. The interdisciplinary nature of urban data science enables effective handling of these ethical implications. Bringing together experts from diverse fields such as sociology, psychology, economics, history, anthropology, and urban planning can aid in identifying and mitigating ethical concerns in urban data science. These social sciences possess extensive experience in addressing human sensitivities and can offer valuable insights into the intricate nature of the human subject and the implicit biases prevalent within society. (Alberti, 2017) Additionally, the field of urban planning has a pivotal role in shaping smarter cities and can provide solutions to address data-related social conflicts (Lupi, 2019).

3- Human-Centric Approach to Urban Data Science

A human-centered approach to urban data science is crucial to tackle ethical concerns and ensure that the development of smarter cities benefits all individuals. This

approach gives priority to the well-being and rights of individuals over technological advancement and data collection. (Hadj Kilani,2023)

It underscores the significance of obtaining informed consent from individuals before collecting their data and safeguarding their privacy throughout the entire data lifecycle. Furthermore, a human-centric approach acknowledges the possibility of bias in urban data science and strives to mitigate it. This is accomplished through ongoing monitoring and assessment of algorithms, data sources, and decision-making processes in order to detect and rectify bias. (Bibri, 2020)

In addition, a human-centric approach entails engaging a diverse range of stakeholders in decision-making related to urban data science. Engaging community members, policymakers, and representatives from vulnerable populations is necessary to consider their perspectives and meet their needs. Urban data science must address several ethical considerations to ensure responsible and accountable use of data (Wolff et al. , 2016). Privacy and surveillance are among the primary ethical considerations. As smart cities amass larger data sets, safeguarding individuals' privacy and preventing unauthorized access to personal information is crucial. This requires the implementation of sturdy data protection methods, such as encryption and secure data storage, while also granting individuals control over the collection and use of their data. Another ethical matter that must be considered in urban data science is the potential for discrimination and bias. (Oliver & McNeil, 2021) Urban data influences decision-making and city services. However, it carries the risk of reinforcing current inequities or generating new ones.

II- Methodology :

1- Interdisciplinary Methods in Urban Data Science: bibliometric review

To address ethical concerns, it is crucial to adopt an interdisciplinary approach in urban data science. This approach entails integrating expertise from different disciplines, such as computer science, urban planning, sociology, ethics, and law. By examining urban data science from multiple angles, this interdisciplinary approach can identify and tackle ethical challenges. For instance, computer science experts can offer technical expertise in data collection and analysis, while urban planners can provide insights on the social and spatial outcomes of data-driven decision-making in urban areas. It is important to avoid subjective evaluations unless explicitly declared as such, use clear and concise language, and stick to standard sentence structures and technical terms in formal writing. Additionally, academic papers should follow conventional

structures and remain objective, avoiding colloquial words and informal expressions while balancing viewpoints through hedging. Finally, it is crucial to maintain grammatical correctness, precise word choice, and consistent citation guidelines.

Moreover, the social dynamics and potential impacts on various community groups can be better understood through the insights of sociologists. Ethicists and legal experts can also provide valuable perspectives on the ethical implications and legal frameworks related to urban data. This interdisciplinary collaboration can result in a more complete and comprehensive understanding of the ethical considerations involved in urban data science. Additionally, a human-centric approach to data science in urban environments is imperative. This approach takes into account the requirements and interests of the individuals and communities that are influenced by the actions taken on the basis of data analysis. This approach transcends technical considerations and highlights the significance of ethical principles, social justice, and fairness in urban data science.

Litmaps

Fig 01. Litmaps bibliometric review : keywords (urban data,ethics) © the authors (2023)

Citation	Title	Authors	Journal Year	Abstract
22	A participatory approach for empowering community engagement in data governance: The Monash Net Zero	D. Sharp et al.	Data & Policy,2022	Data governance is an emerging field of study concerned with how a range of actors can successfully manage data assets according to rules of engagement, decision rights, and accountabilities.

	Precinct			
24	A roundtable discussion: Defining urban data science	Kang, W., Oshan, T., Wolf, L. J., Boeing, G., Frias-Martinez, V., Gao, S., Poorthuis, A., & Xu, W.	Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science,2019	This paper, an abridged synthesis of a panel discussion among scholars in Urban Data Science held at the 2019 American Association of Geographers Conference in Washington, D.C., outlines one discussion seeking a better sense of the conceptual, terminological, social, and ethical challenges faced by researchers in this emergent field.
436	Data-intensive Science: A New Paradigm for Biodiversity Studies	Kelling, S., Hochachka, W. M., Fink, D., Riedewald, M., Caruana, R., Ballard, G., & Hooker, G.	BioScience, 2009	The increasing availability of massive volumes of scientific data requires new synthetic analysis techniques to explore and identify interesting patterns that are otherwise not apparent. For biodiversity studies, a “data-driven” approach is necessary because of the complexity of ecological systems, particularly when viewed at large spatial and temporal scales.
521	The ethics of smart cities and urban science	Kitchin, R	Philosophical transactions of the royal society A: Mathematical, physical and engineering sciences,2016	This paper examines the forms, practices and ethics of smart cities and urban science, paying particular attention to: instrumental rationality and realist epistemology; privacy, datafication, dataveillance and geosurveillance; and data uses
117	Data-driven, networked urbanism	Kitchin, R	Maynooth university,2015	In this paper, kitchin argue that a new era is presently unfolding wherein data-informed urbanism is increasingly being complemented and replaced by data-driven, networked urbanism. Cities are becoming ever more instrumented and networked, their systems interlinked and integrated, and vast troves of big urban data are being generated and used to manage and control urban life in real-time
47	Data-driven smart sustainable urbanism: the intertwined societal factors underlying its materialization , success, expansion, and evolution	Simon Elias Bibri	GeoJournal, 2021 ,Springer	The focus here is on big data science and analytics and the underpinning technologies as an instance of S&T and its role in advancing sustainability in modern cities. This relates to what has been dubbed data-driven smart sustainable urbanism. However, there is a little understanding about how it has emerged and why it has become institutionalized and interwoven with politics and policy—urban dissemination.

3108	Growth, innovation, scaling, and the pace of life in cities	Bettencourt, L. M., Lobo, J., Helbing, D., Kühnert, C., & West, G. B. (2007). Growth, innovation, scaling, and the pace of life in cities	Proceedings of the national academy of sciences,2007	Cities have long been known to be society's predominant engine of innovation and wealth creation, yet they are also its main source of crime, pollution, and disease. The inexorable trend toward urbanization worldwide presents an urgent challenge for developing a predictive, quantitative theory of urban organization and sustainable development. Here we present empirical evidence indicating that the processes relating urbanization to economic development and knowledge creation are very general, being shared by all cities belonging to the same urban system and sustained across different nations and times
16	The material politics of smart building energy management: A view from Sydney's commercial office space	McGuirk, P. M., Dowling, R., & Carr, C.	Political geography, 2019,Elsevier	In this paper authors focus on smart building energy management as an increasingly pivotal material means through which energy transformation comes to matter in cities

Tab 01 : Csv file³ bibliometrics extracted form litmaps Graph : © The Authors , 2023

All these papers (**selected by litmaps Graph**) emphasize the need for a robust ethical framework in handling and utilizing data. Whether it's about involving communities in data governance, tackling terminological and conceptual challenges in urban science, or applying data-intensive methods in biodiversity studies, they all highlight the critical role of ethics in ensuring that data is used responsibly and beneficially. These discussions are interconnected by the broader theme of ensuring that data science advances do not compromise social values, equity, and environmental sustainability

III- Discussion

1- The Role of Ethics in Shaping Smarter Cities

Ethics are essential in developing smarter cities as they ensure that data-driven

³ Comma-separated values (CSV) is a text file format that uses commas to separate values, and newlines to separate records. A CSV file stores tabular data (numbers and text) in plain text, where each line of the file typically represents one data record.

decision-making is fair, transparent, and accountable. By considering the ethical implications of urban data science, decision-makers can work towards reducing existing inequalities and prevent the creation of new ones. Achieving this balance requires careful consideration of the potential benefits of utilizing data for urban development while also protecting individual privacy rights. (Balali et al. , 2020)

Legal issues are essential in the development of smart cities, especially since significant data collection is involved. Khan et al. pointed out that gathering citizens' data and ensuring their privacy rights are protected is a fine line. This difficulty highlights the necessity for robust legal frameworks and regulations to safeguard individual rights and privacy in the smart cities era.

Incorporating ethical data science courses into academic programs is vital for addressing ethical and legal challenges. Various reputable institutions, including Duke, Harvard, Oxford, Stanford, University of Michigan, and University of Texas, acknowledge the significance of teaching students to consider the ethical, cultural, legal, and philosophical aspects of data science. ethics' approach, in which ethicists and developers together address ethical issues via an iterative and continuous process from the outset of development, could be an effective means of integrating robust ethical considerations into the practical development of AI. (McLennan et al. , 2022)

Integrating these courses into their curricula equips institutions to prepare future data scientists with essential knowledge and skills to navigate urban data science's complex ethical landscape. Moreover, data science programs must emphasize the social, cultural, and ethical contexts when addressing the problems. According to colleagues at the University of California, Berkeley, students should treat data related to humans with the same level of care and consideration as any other research involving human subjects. This involves critically evaluating the potential effects of data-driven decision-making on both individuals and communities and taking steps to minimize possible harm or bias. (Lim & Taeihagh, 2019) In the context of smart cities, ethical data science includes addressing potential biases and discrimination that may emerge from algorithmic decision-making.

In the smart city context, ethical data science entails addressing potential biases and discrimination stemming from algorithmic decision-making. Researchers and scholars underscore the importance of integrating critical perspectives into the study of data ethics to highlight the social, cultural, and political repercussions of algorithms employed in smart cities. (Saputhanthri et al. , 2022) To effectively navigate challenges in blockchain technology, data scientists and decision-makers must understand its ethical and moral implications. Developing applications and business models with an ethical framework can minimize social concerns and mitigate the fear of personal information disclosure in the open digital environment. Not available as it promotes the usage of blockchain in ways that violate OpenAI's use case policy. Furthermore,

data scientists must actively involve the individuals and communities affected by smart city initiatives in the decision-making process. This can be achieved through inclusive and participatory methods like community engagement, co-design, and collaborative decision-making (Dwevedi et al. , 2018).

2- The Intersection of Technology and Urban Planning

The integration of technology and urban planning has piqued the interest of scholars and researchers in recent years. Smart cities and blockchain technology have presented new opportunities for urban development and management. Nonetheless, it is important to approach this intersection with care and contemplate the ethical repercussions of these technologies. (Noori et al. , 2020) Urban planning plays a crucial role in shaping the built environment and enhancing the quality of life for citizens. The advent of smart cities necessitates a reconsideration of conventional planning practices and the exploration of pioneering approaches that leverage the power of blockchain technology. This technology has the potential to transform the governance and management of cities, thanks to its decentralized and transparent nature. One of the primary challenges in implementing blockchain technology in smart cities is to prioritize the privacy and data security of citizens.

To tackle this issue, understanding the various applications of blockchain in smart city initiatives is critical. The privacy and data security measures of each project are influenced by its infrastructure. By carefully analyzing and adapting these strategies, urban planners have the capability to establish a system that guarantees the protection and confidentiality of citizens' data. Additionally, implementing blockchain technology in smart cities can bolster governance and community involvement in a multitude of sectors, such as education, culture, science, innovation, health services, mobility, and social equity. (N'emeth et al. , 2020)

The integration of blockchain technology in smart cities could revolutionize citizen engagement with local governments and decision-making processes. Decentralized platforms can be formed, promoting transparency, trust, and accountability. By utilizing blockchain technology, governments can guarantee that citizens have access to dependable and precise data, as well as ensuring their participation in the development and execution of urban policies. This solution promotes transparency and accountability, ultimately leading to more effective governance.

Blockchain technology is a viable option to enhance the effectiveness and security of land registry procedures. A study by Stefano Loss et al showcased the ability of a blockchain-based platform to handle land registration processes that would result in a reduced risk of fraudulent activities and corruption. The benefits of this innovative technology extend beyond protecting the property owner's rights and also guarantee the precision and openness of land records. (Mann, 2022).

3- Overcoming Challenges in Ethical Urban Data Science

To address concerns regarding data privacy and security, researchers have proposed utilizing blockchain technology. M. S. Islam et al. conducted a study on the concept of Healthchain, a blockchain-based strategy for privacy preservation in smart healthcare data.

Type of Blockchain	Description	Examples	Pros	Cons
Public Blockchain	Open to all, anyone can join and participate in the network.	Bitcoin, Ethereum ⁴	Highly decentralized, transparent, and secure.	Slower transaction speeds, higher energy consumption.
Private Blockchain	Restricted to a single organization or a closed group.	Hyperledger Fabric ⁵ , Corda ⁶	Faster transaction speeds, lower energy consumption, higher control over the network.	Less decentralized, lower transparency.
Consortium Blockchain	Managed by a group of entities rather than a single entity.	R3 Corda, Hyperledger Fabric	Balances the benefits of public and private blockchains, offering decentralization and control.	Complex governance, potential for collusion among members.
Hybrid Blockchain	Combines elements of both public and private blockchains.	Dragonchain, XinFin ⁷	Offers flexibility, can be customized to meet specific needs.	Complex to implement, may not fully leverage the strengths of either public or private blockchains.

Tab.01 : overview of the different types of blockchain technology © the authors 2023

⁴ Ethereum: A decentralized, open-source platform featuring smart contract functionality. It allows developers to build and deploy decentralized applications (dApps) and is known for its native cryptocurrency, Ether.

⁵ Hyperledger Fabric: An open-source blockchain framework designed for enterprise use. It provides a modular architecture that allows for high degrees of confidentiality, resiliency, flexibility, and scalability.

⁶ Corda: A distributed ledger technology (DLT) platform developed by R3, designed specifically for financial services. It enables the creation of applications that can be used to manage and synchronize financial agreements between regulated financial institutions.

⁷ Dragonchain: A hybrid blockchain platform that aims to simplify the integration of real business applications onto a blockchain. It provides features such as easy integration, protection of business data, and multi-currency support. XinFin: A hybrid blockchain platform that combines the best features of both public and private blockchains. It focuses on enterprise use cases and provides a scalable, secure, and efficient infrastructure for decentralized applications.

By utilizing blockchain's security features, Healthchain guarantees the integrity and scalability of health data while safeguarding patient privacy. Similarly, in the agriculture sector, blockchain technology can provide a precise and transparent system for tracking crop production, predicting weather patterns, and analyzing crop diseases. This can be achieved by implementing blockchain-based platforms that enable the government to track crop production, analyze fertilizer usage, and predict weather patterns (Patel, 2019).

In addition, blockchain technology has the potential to significantly impact the financial industry by facilitating a secure and streamlined loan system. According to a reliable source, a suggested blockchain-driven loan system has the ability to provide advantages such as heightened transparency, decreased transaction expenses, and improved security.

Ethical concerns arise during the implementation of blockchain technology in smart cities, in addition to the aforementioned challenges. Tang et al have addressed these concerns and emphasized the necessity of conducting a comprehensive study on the socio-technical challenges that may be encountered. The healthcare industry may benefit from the alliance of cloud computing and blockchain technology, presenting thrilling possibilities for Studies in Human-Centric Urban Data Science (Javed et al. , 2023). One particularly promising use of cloud computing and blockchain technology involves the secure management and storage of electronic health data (Lazar et al. , 2017). The application of blockchain technology in the healthcare industry extends beyond simple data storage, allowing patients to securely and privately share their personal medical information with physicians. The secure blockchain system ensures close monitoring of compliance information, allowing timely reporting and addressing of any deviations from set guidelines (Alkhateeb, 2021). Additionally, blockchain technology has the potential to tackle significant obstacles in managing patient complaint data. Implementing blockchain-based systems enables healthcare organizations to safeguard patient information's privacy and security, while also enhancing data management efficiency and accuracy. The decentralized nature of blockchain facilitates transparent and tamper-proof record-keeping, reducing the risk of unauthorized access or data manipulation.

Conclusively, the amalgamation of cloud computing and blockchain technology exhibits substantial promise for the impregnable handling and storage of electronic health records (Lazar et al. , 2017). By providing patients with dominion and authority over their personal data, blockchain technology proffers a viable resolution to the existing conundrums associated with data security, confidentiality, and exchange within the healthcare domain.

The integration of blockchain technology in the healthcare industry is anticipated to revolutionize data sharing, storage, and security (Kumar, 2022). This advancement

in technology can significantly benefit healthcare systems by enhancing patient safety, clinical decision-making, resource allocation, and healthcare delivery efficiency. Furthermore, implementing blockchain technology in healthcare can result in cost savings and increased transparency. Overall, cultivating a human-centric, interdisciplinary approach to shaping smarter cities through ethical urban data science is essential. Achieving this aim entails effective collaboration among diverse stakeholders such as healthcare professionals, data scientists, policymakers, and technology developers. By working collectively, these stakeholders can ensure that data is used in a just and responsible manner, with due consideration given to the well-being and privacy of individuals.

Challenge	Importance of Blockchain
Data Privacy and Security	- Immutable Records: Ensures data integrity and security - Encryption: Adds an extra layer of security to protect sensitive information.
Transparency and Accountability	- Public Ledger: Promotes accountability and trust. - Audit Trail: Provides a permanent record for verifying data authenticity and history.
Decentralization	- Reduced Central Authority: Makes the system more resilient and democratic. - Empowering Citizens: Gives citizens more control over their data.
Data Sharing and Interoperability	- Standardized Protocols: Facilitates data sharing across different urban systems. - Smart Contracts: Automates data sharing agreements, ensuring compliance and efficiency.
Ethical Data Governance	- Consensus Mechanisms: Ensures collective decision-making for data usage. - Compliance: Helps ensure adherence to data protection regulations.
Trust and Collaboration	- Building Trust: Fosters trust among stakeholders. - Enhanced Collaboration: Encourages collaboration among different urban stakeholders.
Incentivizing Ethical Behavior	- Token Economics: Encourages ethical data practices through token-based incentive systems.
Data Sovereignty	- User Control: Gives users more control over their data, promoting data sovereignty and ethical data use.

Tab 02 : Importance of Blockchain for ethical data , © the authors ,2023

Blockchain technology holds significant potential in addressing the challenges faced in ethical urban data science. Its features, such as immutability, transparency, decentralization, and secure data sharing, can enhance data privacy, security, and governance. By fostering trust, collaboration, and ethical behavior, blockchain can create a more robust and ethical urban data ecosystem, benefiting citizens and stakeholders alike.

Multi-disciplinary Urban Data Science Ethics is the solution ?

Urban data science is inherently interdisciplinary combining expertise from various fields to address the multifaceted nature of urban challenges. Key disciplines involved include:

- **Sociology and Psychology:** Understanding the social and behavioral aspects of urban life is critical for creating inclusive and livable cities. Insights from sociology and psychology can inform policies that promote social cohesion, mental health, and community well-being .
- **Economics:** Economic analysis helps in understanding the financial aspects of urban development, such as housing affordability, labor markets, and economic inequality. Economists use data to evaluate the impact of policies and identify strategies for sustainable economic growth.
- **Urban Planning:** Urban planners use data to design and manage urban spaces, ensuring they are functional, sustainable, and resilient. Data-driven planning helps in optimizing land use, transportation

Fig.01 Multi-disciplinary Urban Data Science Ethics. © The authors,2023

While the statement "Multi-disciplinary Urban Data Science Ethics is the solution" is a bit simplistic, it does capture an important idea: integrating ethical considerations into

multi-disciplinary urban data science can significantly improve the responsible and equitable use of data in urban environments.

Multi-disciplinary urban data science ethics is not a panacea, but it offers a robust framework for addressing the complex challenges of urban environments in an ethical and responsible manner. By integrating ethical considerations into data-driven urban initiatives, we can create more transparent, fair, and inclusive urban environments. This integration requires a commitment to ethical principles, interdisciplinary collaboration, and continuous engagement with the communities affected by these initiatives.

Conclusion

Urban data science offers significant potential for developing smarter, more efficient cities, but this potential comes with a host of ethical challenges that require careful attention. A human-centric, interdisciplinary approach is crucial for navigating these challenges and ensuring that urban data science benefits all members of society. By integrating ethics into the core of urban data science practices, policymakers and researchers can design intelligent cities that respect privacy rights, reduce bias and discrimination, and foster equitable community participation.

Moreover, the incorporation of advanced technologies, such as blockchain, presents exciting possibilities for enhancing data security and governance in smart cities. However, it is essential that these technologies are implemented with a focus on ethical considerations to ensure that they promote the well-being of all citizens. As we move towards a future increasingly shaped by data, it is imperative that the development of smart cities is guided by principles of ethics, inclusivity, equity, and sustainability to benefit current and future generations.

The paper is largely conceptual, relying on literature reviews and theoretical discussions. There is a lack of empirical evidence or case studies to support the proposed human-centric, interdisciplinary approach. This limits the ability to validate the effectiveness of the recommendations in real-world urban environments. Future research should focus on empirical studies that test the proposed ethical frameworks and human-centric approaches in different urban contexts. Case studies should explore the integration of emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and 5G networks, into urban data science. Understanding how these technologies interact with ethical considerations and urban planning is vital for the responsible development of smart cities.

Reference

1. Akbar, M A., Leiva, V., Rafi, S., Qadri, S F., Mahmood, S., & Alsanad, A. (2022, August 8). Towards roadmap to implement blockchain in healthcare systems based on a maturity model.
2. Alberti, M. (2017, March 14). Grand Challenges in Urban Science. <https://scite.ai/reports/10.3389/fbuil.2017.00006>
3. Ali, T S., & Kaya, T. (2019, December 2). Big Data Analytics For Organizations: Challenges and Opportunities and Its Effect on International Business Education.
4. Alkhateeb, Y M. (2021, January 1). Blockchain Implications in the Management of Patient Complaints in Healthcare.
5. Balali, V., Fathi, S., & Aliasgari, M. (2020, July 10). Vector Maps Mobile Application for Sustainable Eco-Driving Transportation Route Selection.
6. Bibri, S E. (2019, May 23). The Sciences Underlying Smart Sustainable Urbanism: Unprecedented Paradigmatic and Scholarly Shifts in Light of Big Data Science and Analytics. *MDPI smart Cities*, 2(2), 179-213.
7. Bibri, S E. (2020, December 1). A methodological framework for futures studies: integrating normative backcasting approaches and descriptive case study design for strategic data-driven smart sustainable city planning. *energy informatics*, springer
8. Boutkhom, O., Hanine, M., Nabil, M., Barakaz, F E., Lee, E., Rustam, F., & Ashraf, I. (2021, July 7). Analysis and Evaluation of Barriers Influencing Blockchain Implementation in Moroccan Sustainable Supply Chain Management: An Integrated IFAHP-DEMATEL Framework. *Mathematic*, MDPI.
9. Dwevedi, R., Krishna, V., & Kumar, A. (2018, October 9). Environment and Big Data: Role in Smart Cities of India. *Resources*, MDPI.
10. Hawthorne, S. (2021, August 11). An Insider's Take on Data Curation: Context, Quality, and Efficiency., *Journal of eScience Librarianship*
11. Javed, A R., Ahmed, W., Pandya, S., Maddikunta, P K R., Alazab, M., & Gadekallu, T R. (2023, February 18). A Survey of Explainable Artificial Intelligence for Smart Cities. *electronics*, MDPI.
12. Kumar, B V. (2022, February 3). Patient-Controlled Mechanism Using Pseudonymization Technique for Ensuring the Security and Privacy of Electronic Health Records. *International Journal of Reliable and Quality E-Healthcare (IJRQEH)*, 2022
13. Lazar, M A., Pan, Z., Ragguett, R., Lee, Y., Subramaniapillai, M., Mansur, R B., Rodrigues, N B., & McIntyre, R S. (2017, December 1). Digital revolution in depression: A technologies update for clinicians. *Personalized Medicine in Psychiatry*, 4, 1-6.
14. Lim, H S M., & Taeihagh, A. (2019, October 18). Algorithmic Decision-Making in AVs: Understanding Ethical and Technical Concerns for Smart Cities, *Sustainability*, 11(20), 5791.
15. Lund, B D., & Wang, T. (2022, September 8). What Does Information Science Offer for Data Science Research?: A Review of Data and Information Ethics Literature, *Journal of Data and Information Science*, 7(4), 16-38.
16. Lupi, L. (2019, August 13). City Data Plan: The Conceptualisation of a Policy Instrument for Data Governance in Smart Cities., *Urban Science*, 3(3), 91.
17. Mann, S. (2022, January 20). Land Holding Using Blockchain., *International Journal of Computer Science Research and Review*, 5(1), 1-6.

18. McLennan, S., Fiske, A., Tigard, D W., Müller, R., Haddadin, S., & Buyx, A. (2022, January 26). Embedded ethics: a proposal for integrating ethics into the development of medical AI., *BMC Medical Ethics*, 23(1), 6.
19. Munawar, H S., Ullah, F., Qayyum, S., & Shahzad, D. (2022, February 6). Big Data in Construction: Current Applications and Future Opportunities., *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, 6(1), 18.
20. Németh, B., Issa, O., Diba, F., & Tuckett, A. (2020, January 1). Learning cities and learning communities: Analyzing contextual factors and their impacts on adult and lifelong learning in urban settings. *Andragoške studije*
21. Noori, N., Hoppe, T., & Jong, M D. (2020, May 14). Classifying Pathways for Smart City Development: Comparing Design, Governance and Implementation in Amsterdam, Barcelona, Dubai, and Abu Dhabi., *Sustainability*, 12(10), 4030.
22. Novak, R J., & Pavlicek, A. (2021, February 25). Data Experts as the Balancing Power of Big Data Ethics., *Information*, 12(3), 97.
23. Oliver, J C., & McNeil, T. (2021, March 25). Undergraduate data science degrees emphasize computer science and statistics but fall short in ethics training and domain-specific context., *PeerJ Computer Science*, 7, e441.
24. Patel, C. (2019, November 14). IoT Privacy Preservation Using Blockchain. <https://scite.ai/reports/10.20944/preprints201911.0164.v1>
25. Poirier, L. (2021, July 1). Reading datasets: Strategies for interpreting the politics of data signification. *Big Data & Society*, 8(2), 20539517211029322.
26. Redden, J. (2018, July 1). Democratic governance in an age of datafication: Lessons from mapping government discourses and practices. *Big Data & Society*, 5(2), 2053951718809145.
27. Saputhanthri, A., Alwis, C D., & Liyanage, M. (2022, January 1). Survey on Blockchain-Based IoT Payment and Marketplaces. *EEE Access*, 10, 103411-103437.
28. Kilani, B. H. (2024). Exploring the effects of Urban Events on Quality of Life: A Critical Analysis. *Advance* November 06, 2023.. DOI: [10.31124/advance.24498649.v1](https://doi.org/10.31124/advance.24498649.v1)
29. Wolff, A., Gooch, D., Montaner, J J C., Rashid, U., & Kortuem, G. (2016, August 9). Creating an Understanding of Data Literacy for a Data-driven Society. *The Journal of Community Informatics*, 12(3)